

Senior High School Learners' Perception on School Day Duration

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Abstract

This study investigated the perceptions and preferences of senior high school students regarding the optimal length of the school day and its potential impact on student engagement. Recognizing the growing concern over excessively long school hours and their possible effects on learners' well-being and academic efficiency, the research aimed to explore how students experience and evaluate their current school schedules. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the study surveyed 271 senior high school students. The findings revealed that a significant majority of students perceive the current school day, typically lasting 7 to 9.5 hours, as excessively long. Most expressed a preference for a shorter school day of 5 to 6 hours, primarily to allow more time for rest, personal development, and independent study. Students also favored a school start time between 7:00 and 8:00 a.m., highlighting the need for adequate morning preparation. Mid-morning and early morning hours were identified as the most effective periods for learning. Despite extended instructional time, international assessments suggest that academic performance remains low, raising concerns about the efficiency of time spent in school. These findings underscore the importance of aligning school schedules not only with curriculum demands but also with students' cognitive readiness, well-being, and engagement.

Keywords: school day duration, school day length, academic scheduling, senior high school

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1. Introduction

Understanding the optimal length of the school day for maximizing student engagement and learning outcomes has long been a topic of debate among educators and researchers. However, existing research on the impact of school day duration on academic achievement has yielded mixed results, highlighting a complex relationship influenced by various factors. For example, studies have consistently found that socioeconomic status (SES) is a stronger predictor of student performance than school day length, which has shown minimal influence on standardized test scores (Sammarone, 2016; DeAngelis, 2014; Plevier, 2016). This suggests that while time spent in school is important, it may not be the sole factor affecting academic outcomes.

Despite these findings, some research points to a nuanced effect of school day length. While Sammarone (2016) and DeAngelis (2014) reported a small yet statistically significant link between extended school days and improved test scores, Plevier (2016) found no significant correlation. Additional elements, such as student attendance, mobility, disabilities, and staff educational background, have also been shown to play critical roles in influencing academic success (Sammarone, 2016; Plevier, 2016). This suggests that school day length alone may not be a major determinant of academic performance and underscores the importance of considering these other factors.

Notably, Wu (2020) found that longer school days, rather than extended school years, could have a positive impact on students from disadvantaged backgrounds, who benefitted from the "spillover effects" of additional time in non-tested subjects. These findings indicate that school day configuration might contribute to engagement and equity, especially for students in challenging socioeconomic circumstances.

Given this complexity, exploring students' own perceptions and preferences regarding school day duration may shed light on how the structure of the school day aligns with their engagement. By understanding these perspectives, this study seeks to provide insights into the factors students feel contribute to an optimal learning experience, potentially informing more effective school scheduling practices. Furthermore, the aim of this research is to explore learner perceptions and preferences regarding the optimal length of the school day and its potential impact on student engagement. This study seeks to address the gap in the current literature by examining how students feel about the length of their school day. By investigating these factors, the study aims to provide valuable insights that could inform policy decisions on school day structures, ensuring they align with students' needs and contribute to enhanced educational experiences.

2. Review of Literature

Various researches suggest that socioeconomic factors, student attendance, and instructional quality may play a larger role in determining academic outcomes than the sheer number of hours spent in school (Sammarone, 2016; DeAngelis, 2014; Plevier, 2016). However, studies such as Wu (2020) have demonstrated that extended school days can positively impact students, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, by providing additional opportunities for engagement in non-tested subjects. Despite these

findings, gaps remain in understanding how students themselves view the relationship between school day length and their ability to remain engaged, manage their personal time, and achieve academic success.

The optimal length of the school day and its impact on student engagement and academic performance has been a longstanding focus in education research. Comparative studies reveal considerable international variation in school day duration, from approximately 4.5 to 10 hours (World Population Review, 2024). Taiwan has one of the longest school days, averaging 10 hours, while countries such as Finland and Brazil, which prioritize educational efficiency and student well-being, maintain an average school day of 5 hours. Germany's shorter school day of 4.5 hours further illustrates the diversity in educational structures and values across different contexts.

Research on extended learning time (ELT) has produced mixed findings regarding its effectiveness in enhancing academic outcomes. Gurung (2022) found that prolonged school hours did not yield significant improvements in examination performance, suggesting that optimizing instructional time may be more effective than simply increasing it. Similarly, Cattaneo, Oggenfuss, and Wolter (2017) observed that supplementary instructional hours dedicated to remediation, enrichment, or private tutoring did not have a significant impact on achievement unless tailored to individual student needs. Their findings underscore the importance of individualized instructional time, particularly for students with lower academic abilities, who may benefit more from extended hours than higher-achieving peers.

The effectiveness of study hours outside of school further complicates the discussion. Baliyan and Khama (2020) reported that extended study hours positively influenced Mathematics performance but had no significant effect on English achievement, underscoring the importance of subject-specific learning demands. In line with this, Liu (2022) argued that while increased study time correlates with academic performance, the benefits plateau beyond a certain threshold, beyond which additional hours do not significantly contribute to academic gains. This perspective aligns with findings by the OECD (2020), which noted that instructional time in language subjects enhanced reading performance only up to three hours per week, reinforcing the notion that instructional quality may supersede duration.

Evidence also suggests that longer school days may disproportionately benefit socioeconomically disadvantaged students. Wu (2020) observed that lengthening the school day—rather than the school year—yielded substantial benefits for underprivileged students, particularly in providing exposure to non-tested subjects, thus contributing to a more holistic educational experience. In Colombia, Hincapie (2016) demonstrated that an extended school day positively impacted student performance, particularly in Mathematics and among students in disadvantaged rural areas. Likewise, Garcia, Fernandez, and Weiss (2013) found that a transition from half-day to full-day schooling reduced dropout rates and grade repetition, highlighting the socio-academic advantages of increased instructional hours.

However, the impact of additional instruction time is not uniformly positive. Research suggests that an increase in instructional hours may inadvertently exacerbate performance

disparities among students. Huebener, Kuger, and Marcus (2017) noted that extended instructional time can widen achievement gaps between lower- and higher-performing students. Barrios Fernández (2023) similarly cautioned that the quality of in-school learning experiences must be balanced against students' home learning opportunities to maximize benefits, particularly for students with fewer resources.

Despite the potential benefits of lengthened school days, some scholars question its efficacy. Walden University (n.d.) highlighted that although extended school hours could alleviate childcare burdens and increase instructional time, they may also limit students' opportunities for rest, leisure, and extracurricular engagement, which are crucial for holistic development. Supporting this perspective, Sammarone (2014) and DeAngelis (2014) found that factors such as socioeconomic status, student attendance, and teacher qualifications were more substantial predictors of student achievement than school day length. Additionally, Ezeonu et al. (2017) contended that effective time utilization, rather than mere extension, should be the focal point of educational policy.

These varied findings illustrate the complexities inherent in the relationship between school day length and academic outcomes. Current literature suggests that while instructional time is a key educational variable, its structure, content, and alignment with students' developmental needs warrant careful consideration to maximize learning outcomes and ensure equitable educational practices. However, studies based on the point of view of the learners are quite scant, thus, this study aims to explore the learners' perception and preference regarding the length of the school day and the optimal learning time.

3. Method

The aim of this research is to explore learner perceptions and preferences regarding the optimal length of the school day and its potential impact on student engagement. This study seeks to address the gap in the current literature by examining how students feel about the length of their school day. By investigating this factor, the study aims to provide valuable insights that could inform policy decisions on school day structures, ensuring they align with students' needs and contribute to enhanced educational experiences. Through a mixed-methods approach, the research combines quantitative and qualitative data to capture a comprehensive picture of student preferences and the nuanced ways in which school day duration impacts engagement.

3.1. Design of the Study

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design to examine learners' perceptions and preferences regarding school day duration. Previous research on the influence of school day length has employed diverse methodologies, with quantitative studies identifying broad trends in academic performance (Wu, 2020; Sammarone, 2014) and qualitative studies providing in-depth insights into individual experiences and engagement patterns (Gurung, 2022; Liu, 2022). Given the multifaceted nature of this research topic, the integration of both quantitative and qualitative approaches allowed for a comprehensive analysis, capturing general trends while also exploring the contextual factors influencing student engagement.

A mixed-methods approach was particularly suitable for this study as it addressed both measurable outcomes and subjective perceptions, which are essential in understanding complex social phenomena such as student engagement and optimal learning environments (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). The quantitative component consisted of a structured survey designed to measure students' preferred school day duration and perceived engagement levels. The qualitative component included focus groups and individual interviews, which provided deeper insights into the reasons behind students' preferences and the contextual factors affecting their engagement throughout the day.

The selection of this design aligned with prior studies emphasizing the advantages of integrating quantitative and qualitative data in educational research (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). The complementary nature of these methods enabled the study to explore not only what school day length students preferred but also why they felt more or less engaged at different durations. This approach ensured that the findings were both statistically robust and contextually rich, offering a nuanced understanding of student perceptions (Johnson et al., 2007).

Additionally, the study employed a descriptive survey research design to systematically collect data on learners' perceptions and preferences. A descriptive survey design was well-suited for this research as it facilitated the collection of structured data that could be analyzed to describe, explain, and interpret the perspectives of a large population (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This design was particularly appropriate for capturing attitudes, beliefs, and preferences, as it enabled the efficient gathering of data from a broad sample of participants (Fraenkel et al., 2019, as cited in Smolinsky et al., 2022).

The survey instrument utilized a 5-point Likert scale, allowing participants to express their level of agreement or preference on various statements. This approach ensured that the data collection process was efficient and allowed for statistical analysis to identify trends and patterns in learners' perceptions and preferences (Groves et al., 2009). The descriptive survey design supported the study's objective of generating evidence-based insights that can inform school administrators, educators, and policymakers in designing effective and engaging learning environments.

3.2. Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at the Ozamiz City School of Arts and Trades (OCSAT), a public technical-vocational high school located in Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental, Philippines. Established to provide accessible and quality technical-vocational education, OCSAT caters to junior and senior high school students, particularly those enrolled in the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track.

The school is recognized for its diverse offerings of TVL specializations, including Electrical Installation and Maintenance, Automotive Servicing, Plumbing, and Bread and Pastry Production, among others. OCSAT aims to equip learners with the practical skills and competencies required to succeed in industry-specific careers or entrepreneurship upon graduation. The institution also emphasizes aligning its curriculum with labor market demands, ensuring that its graduates are competitive both locally and globally (DepEd, 2021).

Strategically situated in Ozamiz City, OCSAT serves students from various socioeconomic backgrounds, including those from remote barangays and neighboring municipalities. This diversity provided a unique perspective on educational needs, preferences, and challenges, making it an appropriate setting for this research on learners' perceptions and preferences regarding school day duration.

3.3. Respondents of the Study

The respondents included in this study consisted of 271 senior high school students enrolled at the Ozamiz City School of Arts and Trades (OCSAT) during the second semester of School Year 2024–2025. These individuals were selected through availability sampling, ensuring that the study included participants who were accessible and willing to participate at the time of data collection.

The sample represented students from various strands from Academic and TVL tracks offered by the institution, reflecting the diversity of academic and practical workloads within the senior high school curriculum. Given their direct experience with the existing school day structure, the respondents provided valuable insights into how the duration of the school day influenced their engagement, learning experiences, and overall academic performance.

By focusing on respondents from a single semester, the study provided a detailed snapshot of learners' perceptions and preferences during that specific academic period. The use of availability sampling allowed for the efficient collection of relevant data while ensuring that the findings captured a broad range of student perspectives on the optimal school day duration.

4. Results

4.1. Perceived School Day Length

This study reveals that most of the students perceived the school day to be too long, see Figure 1. The perception is measured through a 5-point Likert scale based on their agreement on the statements whether they believe that their school day is too long, too short, or practically balanced. The scoring was 1 = Highly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = Highly Agree. The bars represent the mean scores of the samples, namely, SD Too Long = 3.823, SD Too Short = 2.937 and SD Balanced = 3.605. Based on the group mean, the learners are likely to agree that their school day is too long.

Figure 1. Perception of Learners on School Day Length

Legend: SD = School Day

Note: 1.00 = Strongly Disagree ... 5.00 = Strongly Agree

To determine whether there is a significant difference between the three treatments (SD Too Long, SD Too Short and SD Balanced), a repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted. Since Mauchly's test of sphericity indicated that the assumption of sphericity is violated ($p < .05$), Greenhouse-Geisser sphericity correction was employed, and the repeated measures ANOVA yielded a p -value of $< .001$. With this, it is safe to assume that there was a significant difference among the repeated measure factors. See Table 1 for reference.

Table 1. Repeated Measures ANOVA of Perceptions of Learners on School Day (SD)

Within Subjects Effects							
Cases	Sphericity Correction	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	
Perceptions on SD Length	Greenhouse-Geisser	115.427	1.942	59.432	77.931	< .001	
Residuals	Greenhouse-Geisser	399.907	524.387	0.763			

Note: Type III Sum of Squares

^a Mauchly's test of sphericity indicates that the assumption of sphericity is violated ($p < .05$).

Descriptives						
Perceptions on SD Length	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation	
SD Too Long	271	3.823	0.872	0.053	0.228	
SD Too Short	271	2.937	0.996	0.061	0.339	
SD Balanced	271	3.605	0.875	0.053	0.243	

<i>Test of Sphericity</i>							
	Mauchly's W	Approx. χ^2	df	p-value	Greenhouse-Geisser ϵ	Huynh-Feldt ϵ	Lower Bound ϵ
Perceptions on SD Length	0.970	8.131	2	0.017	0.971	0.978	0.500

<i>Post Hoc Comparisons - Perceptions on SD Length</i>							
		Mean Difference	SE	df	t	p_{bonf}	p_{holm}
SD Too Long	SD Too Short	0.886	0.074	540	11.979	< .001	< .001
	SD Balanced	0.218	0.074	540	2.945	0.010	0.003
SD Too Short	SD Balanced	-0.668	0.074	540	-9.034	< .001	< .001

Note: P-value adjusted for comparing a family of 3 estimates.

<i>Conover's Post Hoc Comparisons - Perceptions on SD Length</i>									
		T-Stat	df	W_i	W_j	r_{rb}	p	p_{bonf}	p_{holm}
SD Too Long	SD Too Short	12.039	540	619.000	417.500	0.793	< .001	< .001	< .001
	SD Balanced	1.763	540	619.000	589.500	0.254	0.079	0.236	0.079
SD Too Short	SD Balanced	10.277	540	417.500	589.500	-0.689	< .001	< .001	< .001

Note: Grouped by subject.
Note: Rank-biserial correlation based on individual signed-rank tests.

4.2. Preferred School Day Length

Figure 2 illustrates that most of the learners favor the school day to be 5-6 hours in length. The option of 6-7 hours comes next with near differences to less than 5 hours and 7-8 hours. A few selected 8-9 hours, more than 10 hours and 9-10 hours.

Figure 2. Preferred School Day Length

The correlation and dependence of the preferred school day length with the perceived school day length were tested. Table 2 indicates that, pairwise, the learners' preference for the school day length has no significant correlation and dependence with both the learners' perceived too long school day (0.409; 0.399) and too short school day (0.691; 0.660). However, paired with the perceived practically balanced school day, although there exists a high significance, the correlation (0.186) and dependence (0.158) are both practically negligible.

Table 2. Correlation between Preferred School Day Length and Perceived School Day Length

Correlation Table			Spearman		Kendall	
			rho	p	tau B	P
Preferred School Day Length	-	Believes School Day is Too Long	-0.050	0.409	-0.043	0.399
Preferred School Day Length	-	Believes School Day is Too Short	0.024	0.691	0.022	0.660
Preferred School Day Length	-	Believes School Day is Practically Balanced	0.186	0.002	0.158	0.002

4.3. Learner’s Reason for Preferred School Day Length

Based on the data obtained from the qualitative question, what was the reason for the student’s preference of school day length, Figure 3 shows that the three most dominant are for resting and relaxing (frequency = 25), doing other tasks or activities (frequency = 20), and learning more or improving academic skills (frequency = 14). Some students consider prefer their school day duration because they like to be at school (frequency =4), some prefer to stay at home (frequency = 3), and others just because they have nothing to do at home (frequency = 1).

Figure 3. Reason for Preferred School Day Length

Note: The data presented are coded from the original responses.

Blank, “none,” “no comment,” and/or other non-related responses were not included.

4.4. Preferred Start of School

Figure 4 illustrates that learners mostly preferred to start school between 7 – 8 a.m. The second preference is between 8 – 9 a.m., followed with between 6 – 7 a.m. and then the other times or periods of the day which all have lower than 20% of the learners’ preference.

Figure 4. Preferred Time to Start School

To check whether the preference on the start of school day is correlated with the perceived school day length and measure the strength of dependence, Spearman's rho and Kendall's tau-b were run, see results in Table 3.

Table 3. Correlation between Preferred Start of School and Perceived School Day Length

Correlation Table				Spearman		Kendall	
				rho	p	tau B	p
Preferred Start of School	-	Believes School Day is Too Long		0.047	0.444	0.036	0.494
Preferred Start of School	-	Believes School Day is Too Short		-0.323	< .001	-0.278	< .001
Preferred Start of School	-	Believes School Day is Practically Balanced		-0.243	< .001	-0.211	< .001

Table 3 indicates that there is no significant correlation (0.047) between the learners' preference on the time to start the school day and their perception that the school day is too long. Additionally, the learners' perception of the school day being too long has no significant dependence (0.036) on their preference for the start of school and vice versa.

Conversely, the learners' preference is found to have negatively low (-0.323) but significant (< .001) correlation with the perception that school day is too short and found to have similar values on dependence (-278; < .001). However, despite having significant value (< .001) between preferred start of school and believing that school day is practically

balanced, the correlation (-0.243) between the two are considerably negligible, so as their dependence (-0.211).

4.5. Learner’s Reason for Preferred Start of School

Based on the data obtained from the qualitative question, what was the reason for the student’s preference on school day length, Figure 5 illustrates that students’ most dominant reason for their preference on the time to start school is for them to have enough time to prepare before school (frequency = 20) which includes reviewing lessons, doing assignments, eating breakfast, having enough travel time, taking a bath, and other similar activities. Some learners prefer early activity (frequency = 12), some want enough sleep and well-rested (frequency = 10), some have to do household chores (frequency = 9), and some just want to have more focus on learning (frequency = 7). Furthermore, some learners just prefer later activity (frequency = 4), some want to do activities not related to academics and home (frequency = 3), some want to have more time to study outside school hours (frequency = 2), and some just because of the weather condition (frequency = 2) being later time of the day is hotter than early morning.

Figure 5. Reasons for Preferred Time to Start School

Note: The data presented are coded from the original responses.

Blank, “none,” “no comment,” and/or other non-related responses were not included.

4.6. Perceived Optimal Learning Time

Figure 6 illustrates that most of the learners believe that the optimal time for learning is in the mid-morning (within 08:30 until 10:30) and the early morning (within 05:00 until 08:30). Moreover, the other times or periods of the day were not likely favored by the learners themselves. Thus, late morning down to nighttime were all less likely selected at below 20%.

Figure 6. *Perceived Time of the Day for Optimal Learning*

Note: The categorization of time herein is based on the context of the learners, which is as follows:

- Early morning = 05:00-08:30
- Mid-morning = 08:30-10:30
- Late morning = 10:30-12:00
- Early afternoon = 13:00-14:30
- Mid-afternoon = 14:30-16:00
- Late afternoon = 16:00-18:00
- Nighttime = beyond 18:00.

The correlation between the perceived optimal learning time and the perceived school day length was tested, with its results presented in Table 4. Whether the learners view the school as too long, too short or practically balanced, there is no significant correlation or dependence on any pairing to the learners' perceived optimal learning time.

Table 4. Correlation between Perceived Optimal Learning Time and Perceived School Day Length

Correlation Table			Spearman		Kendall	
			rho	p	tau B	p
Perceived Optimal Learning Time	-	Believes School Day is Too Long	0.010	0.875	0.007	0.889
Perceived Optimal Learning Time	-	Believes School Day is Too Short	-0.205	< .001	-0.176	< .001
Perceived Optimal Learning Time	-	Believes School Day is Practically Balanced	-0.070	0.254	-0.060	0.258

4.7. Summary of Results

The results of the study revealed several key insights into learners' perceptions and preferences regarding school day duration. A majority of the learners perceived the current school day to be excessively long and expressed a preference for a shorter academic schedule, specifically favoring a school day lasting between 5 to 6 hours.

The primary reasons cited by the learners for preferring a shorter school day included the desire for time to relax and rest, engage in non-academic tasks such as hobbies and household responsibilities, and allocate more time for self-directed study or additional learning. These motivations highlight the importance students place on balancing academic obligations with personal well-being and holistic development.

In terms of school start times, most learners indicated a preference for beginning classes between 7:00 and 8:00 a.m. This preference was mainly rooted in the need for adequate preparation before school, encompassing activities such as reviewing lessons, completing assignments, eating breakfast, commuting, and other morning routines.

Statistical analysis showed that learners' preferred school start time had a low but fairly significant negative correlation with the perception that the school day is too short, suggesting that as preferred start times get later, the likelihood of perceiving the school day as too short slightly decreases. However, both correlation and dependence values remained low.

Furthermore, the majority of learners identified mid-morning (08:30 to 10:30 a.m.) and early morning (05:00 to 08:30 a.m.) as the most optimal periods for learning. Interestingly, no significant correlation or dependence was found between learners' perceived optimal learning time and their perception of the overall length of the school day, indicating that preferences for effective learning periods may be influenced by factors other than the total hours spent in school.

5. Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

5.1. Discussion

The results of this study revealed that majority of the learners perceived the current school day, typically lasting 7 to 9.5 hours, as excessively long. Most students expressed a preference for a shortened school day lasting between 5 to 6 hours. Their dominant reasons centered on the need for rest, time for non-academic pursuits, and opportunities for additional study outside structured instruction. This perception is aligned with the study of Dabbay and Largoza (2024), which concluded that K–12 students in the Philippines are overburdened by longer school days compared to their counterparts in other Southeast Asian nations, exceeding the durations recommended by international education bodies (Testu, 2008).

The preferred school start time among learners was between 7:00 and 8:00 a.m., primarily to allow adequate preparation before attending classes. Furthermore, the perceived optimal learning periods were identified as mid-morning (8:30–10:30 a.m.) and early morning (5:00–8:30 a.m.), consistent with existing research highlighting the importance of aligning school schedules with students' cognitive readiness and circadian rhythms (Lenard et al., 2020; Minges & Redeker, 2016; Sabaoui et al., 2022).

Despite these extended school hours, recent international assessments raise concerns about educational efficiency. According to the OECD (2024), Filipino 15-year-olds scored well below the OECD average in mathematics (355 vs. 472), reading (347 vs. 476), and science (356 vs. 485). Only 16% of students reached the minimum proficiency level in mathematics, and nearly 25% had repeated a grade level—more than double the OECD average. These statistics suggest that extended instructional time, when poorly structured or misaligned with students' needs, does not inherently translate into improved academic outcomes.

Furthermore, comparative data on educational practices and national wellbeing underscores the broader implications of school day duration. Finland, a global benchmark in education, maintains a typical school day length of five hours and reported a world happiness score of 7.74. In contrast, the Philippines—with significantly longer school days—reported a lower happiness score of 6.05 (World Population Review, 2024a; 2024b). This disparity may reflect the broader effects of excessive academic pressure on student wellbeing and life satisfaction.

5.2. Conclusion

This study confirms that most senior high school learners at Ozamiz City School of Arts and Trades find the current school day too long and would prefer a shorter duration, ideally lasting 5 to 6 hours. Their preferences stem not from academic disengagement but from a desire for a more balanced routine that includes rest, personal development, and self-directed learning. The lack of significant correlation between perceived optimal learning time and school day length further supports the argument that academic effectiveness hinges more on the quality and alignment of instruction than on the quantity of instructional hours.

5.3. Recommendations

Based on the findings and claims from the existing literature, it is recommended that educational policymakers and school administrators consider reevaluating the current school day structure. The majority of the learners in this study expressed that the school day is too long and preferred a daily schedule of 5 to 6 hours. This aligns with recommendations from international studies suggesting that excessively long school days may lead to decreased academic engagement and increased learner fatigue (Dabbay & Largoza, 2024; Testu, 2008). Schools may benefit from adopting a more learner-centered schedule that allows sufficient time for rest, extracurricular activities, and independent learning. Moreover, educational institutions may explore flexible or staggered starting times, as learners indicated a preference to begin classes between 7:00 and 8:00 a.m. to allow for adequate preparation time.

Given that longer school days in the Philippines have not translated into improved academic performance, as evidenced by the 2022 PISA results (OECD, 2024), it is advisable to maybe shift focus from extending school hours to enhancing the quality and efficiency of instruction within a shorter, optimized timeframe. Additional consultation with students and teachers should also be conducted regularly to evaluate the effectiveness of school scheduling practices and ensure they align with students' developmental, academic, and psychosocial needs.

5.4. Limitations and Areas of Further Research

This study was limited to senior high school students enrolled during the second semester of School Year 2024–2025 at Ozamiz City School of Arts and Trades. As such, findings may not be generalizable to all senior high school students in other regions or educational settings. The use of availability sampling may also introduce bias, as participation depended on respondents' willingness and accessibility.

Future research may expand to include students from other schools, grade levels, or regions to gain broader insights. Longitudinal studies exploring how perceptions of school day length affect academic performance and well-being over time are also recommended. Additionally, experimental or quasi-experimental designs could assess the impact of varying school day durations on specific learning outcomes.

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Conflict of Interest

The researchers declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the conduct and publication of this study. No financial, personal, or institutional interests influenced the outcomes, interpretations, or reporting of the findings. This research was conducted solely for academic purposes and in pursuit of contributing to educational knowledge and practice.

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